

ARE COMPRESSION STOCKINGS HELPFUL IN VARICOSE VEIN TREATMENT?

For **varicose vein treatment** compression stockings are a short-term solution for a larger issue. But they are very useful though. If you are applying **vein treatments** and currently dealing with varicose veins then use the compression stockings in order to make the veins less visible. This will reduce the damage and can be useful. In order to get rid of the problem, you should be using a treatment.

After a certain age, especially during pregnancy, varicose veins are often a huge problem. [Varicose vein treatment california](#) provides you the right approach to follow and you can be gotten rid of this venous problem. As a reactive short-term solution, many women are using compression stockings for varicose veins. They do not want to treat the root problem. This will cause you more harm than good, this is not helpful in the long run. There are a lot better ways to deal with the issue but it is not necessary to go for surgery always.

There is only one method, which successfully works for varicose veins, and that is to work with your own body - not against it. That means that you give your body the proper tools, that it needs, in order to cure the problem on its own. Removing the veins surgically does work, but your cardiovascular function will be impaired, and the procedure should not be taken lightly, as it is major surgery of large parts of the body. The veins in the legs return blood from the tissues, but if the veins are removed, your blood will still circulate. Just not as effectively. You should think about the risks, before attempting any such procedure.

How do compression stockings work?

On your veins, the pressure is being put by the compression stockings which increases blood flow from your legs. There are three kinds of compression stockings:

1. Prescription-strength gradient compression hose, which offers the greatest amount of pressure to the feet, ankles, and lower legs. You may need a prescription from your **vein doctor** to buy them, especially if your insurance plan covers it. You might need someone who is trained to do this.
2. Over-the-counter gradient compression hose, which gives a little more pressure around the foot, ankle, and lower leg, where pressure is needed most to move the blood back toward your heart.

3. Support pantyhose, which gives the least amount of pressure. These are sold in most stores.

If you have certain types of heart disease, then stronger compression stockings can hurt you. Ask your [vein doctor California](#) or nurse if it's safe for you to use prescription-strength compression stockings or what strength would be safe for you.

Compression stockings can be expensive. It may take you a while to get used to them, as they are hard to put on. If they are fitting right in you, then they should be comfortable. If you have a problem wearing stocks then be sure to seek help from **vein treatment near me**. Until your doctor suggests, avoid elastic bandages for varicose veins. Because they can cut off blood flow and this results in worsen varicose veins.